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USE OF OMEGA-3 FATTY ACIDS FOOD SUPPLEMENTS BY THE YOUNGEST POPULATION OF REPUBLIC OF SERBIA AND REPUBLIC OF SRPSKA– A PILOT SURVEY

Maja Hitl¹, Jelena Banović Fuentes¹, Katarina Bijelić¹, Relja Suručić², Mirjana Đermanović^{2,3}, Nebojša Kladar^{1,4}, Ljilja Torović^{1,4}

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Introduction: Omega -3 fatty acids (OFA) are a group of essential nutrients commonly found in fatty fish. The intake of OFA is considered crucial for normal physiological development, especially in the first two years of life. The study aim was to investigate the use of OFA supplements in the youngest population.

Materials and methods: The study was performed as prospective, cross-section survey in a form of questionnaire, distributed via Internet. It included parents of babies and/or children who are no older than three years, being residents of Serbia and Republic of Srpska.

Results: A total of 42 parents in Serbia and 32 parents in R. Srpska were included in the study. Out of them, 23 parents in Serbia and 20 parents in R. Srpska declared that they give their babies/children supplements containing OFA. In Serbia, parents opted giving these supplements mainly because they believe that they improve brain development and cognitive functions, while parents in R. Srpska stated that they give these supplements because these nutrients are lacking in today's usual diet. In both of regions, supplements are mainly given on a daily basis and continuously (for more than 3 months). Regarding the daily doses, the parents of both regions follow the dosing recommendations given by manufacturers of supplements. In more than 90% of cases (in both regions) the advice on use of OFA came from health professionals.

Conclusions: Parents of both regions reported the use of OFA supplements, while the patterns of use can be qualified as satisfactory. Further promotion of OFA supplements to parents should be encouraged.

Keywords: omega-3 fatty acid, survey, food supplement, children

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